

1 **Fbox control by papillomavirus E6/E7.**

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6 We demonstrate here by RNA-sequencing of keratinocytes containing engineered over-expression of the
7 E6 and E7 papillomavirus oncogenes control of Fbox family genes *Fbxo17* and *Fbxl19* by HPVE6/E7.

8 Citations

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